

AUTECOLOGY OF *CAREX BRIZOIDES* IN WOODLANDS OF THE SILESIA UPLAND AND ITS PHYTOINDICATIVE IMPORTANCE

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Abstract: The objective of the study is to give a detailed characteristics of habitat requirements of *Carex brizoides* in woodlands in the Silesian Upland. The investigations were carried out in forest phytocoenoses, which were chosen according to the presence of *C. brizoides*. In patches of forest communities with *C. brizoides* measurements of slope aspect and inclination and light conditions were taken. Moreover, soil samples from the rhizosphere of sedge were collected and litter depth was measured. The results were presented on ecodiagrams, and on their basis, it was attempted to determine ecological optima of the species studied. The obtained results were compared with values of ecological indicators after ZARZYCKI et al. (2002) and ELLENBERG et al. (1992), commonly used in indirect estimation of habitat conditions. Based on 344 soil samples taken from 172 sites with *C. brizoides*, it was revealed that the sedge most frequently occurred in phytocoenoses with litter depth 2–4 cm, three cover 60–80% and pH (KCl) between 4.4 and 5.0. It was evidenced that our results are considerably different from ecological optima given by Zarzycki and Ellenberg. These differences resulted probably from local character of the presented studies and anthropogenic origin of phytocoenoses analyzed. The results indicated that phytoindicative importance of *C. brizoides* is limited.

Key words: phytoindication, autecology, *Carex brizoides*, forest communities, Silesian Upland.

INTRODUCTION

The massive occurrence of *Carex brizoides* in forests is a common phenomenon noted for several decades in many regions of Poland (e.g. PACZOSKI 1900, HEREŹNIAK 1993, SIERKA and CHMURA 2004, 2006) and in neighbouring countries (e.g. BULKONOW 1975, van DER VEEN and BREMER 1997). As it was shown in previous studies, phytocoenoses with herb layer dominated by this sedge are species-poor (DZWONKO and GAWROŃSKI 1994, FALIŃSKI 1998a, 1998b, STACHURSKA 1998, SIERKA 2003) and more homogenous in terms of physiognomy (KROTOSKA and PIOTROWSKA 1962). These features are considered as characteristic for ceaspitization, a degeneration form of forest (OLACZEK 1974). Most information on habitats with the occurrence of *Carex brizoides* came from floristic and phytosociological surveys (e.g. IZDEBSKI 1972, CELIŃSKI et al. 1978, ANIOŁ-KWIATKOWSKA 1993, HEREŹNIAK 1993, CELIŃSKI and CZYŁOK 1995, STACHURSKA 1998, SIERKA 2003, CHMURA and SIERKA 2007). These studies, however, do not contain detailed autecological data. As ROO-ZIELIŃSKA (2004) reported, investigations based on separate analysis of ecological factors have major application for estimation of plant resources, control methods of their expansion and broadening the concept of phytoindication (DIEKMAN 2003).

Therefore, the subject of present paper is the analysis of the occurrence of the sedge in forest communities of the Silesian Upland at the background of environmental conditions.

The aims of this study are: (1) to determine ranges and optima of habitat conditions in sites with *Carex brizoides* in forest communities in the Silesian Upland and (2) to indicate eventual possibilities of the use of the species in phytoindication.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The fieldwork was conducted in 1998–2001, in the area of the Silesia Upland which covers 3925 km² (KONDRACKI 1994). The Silesian Upland comprises 5 mesoregions (Fig. 1) and is geologically diversified. Upper Carboniferous rocks are the main geological structures of this area, essential to the economy of the region. They are overlaid by a thick layer of postglacial matter, such as sand, gravel and clay. Diversity, distribution and condition of forest communities, which cover approximately 20% of the area, are closely related to the character of habitats and to the type and intensity of human impact (CELIŃSKI et al. 1991).

In patches of forest communities where *Carex brizoides* was recorded, the following habitat conditions were measured: slope, aspect, light (expressed by the cover of tree layer). The cover of tree layer was expressed as a ratio of area covered by crowns to the whole area (SCAMONI 1967). The cover of tree stand as an indicator of light conditions is a commonly used method that gives biased results related to a given research worker (e.g. SŁOMKA 1958).

For detailed laboratory analyses, taking into account seasonal properties of soils (IZDEBSKI et al. 1976), soil samples were taken from rhizosphere of *C. brizoides*, i.e. ca. 10 cm. Litter depth was also measured. The samples were taken two times, in various weather conditions and in different parts of growing season (SZWED 1986, WĘGLARSKI 1991).

In total, 344 soil samples from 172 stands of *C. brizoides* in distinct types of forest communities were collected. In laboratory analyses basic physical and chemical soil properties, ecologically important for growth and development of plants, were taken into account (CZARNECKA 1986, DOBRZAŃSKI et al. 1987):

- 1) humidity – a method based on mass decrement after dessication in 105°C,
- 2) pH – measured in solution of KCl and in distilled water,
- 3) granulometric composition – by a method by Cassagrande modified by Prószyński (DOBRZAŃSKI and UZIĄK 1970),
- 4) organic carbon – by Tiurin method,
- 5) total nitrogen – by Kjeldahl method (PN-ISO 11261),
- 6) content of available phosphorous and potassium – by Egner method modified by Rheim (PN-R-04023),
- 7) content of available magnesium – by Schatschabel method (PN-R-04020),
- 8) ratio C:N based on percentage of both elements.

The results of analyses were presented in the form of ecodiagrams (ZARZYCKI et al. 2002). The ecodiagrams show distribution of frequency of the species in various classes of values of ecological factors (WĘGLARSKI 1991). The presented ecodiagrams allow determining ecological optima and phytoindicative value of the species

Fig. 1. Localization of the study area (KONDRACKI 1994, modified): 1 – forests, 2 – towns.

studied. It is assumed that ecological optimum of the species concerns this class of a given variable (Table 1), where the highest frequency is noted (SZWED 1986). Eco-diagrams is as a widely used graphical method of presentation in ecological studies (e.g. GRIME and LLOYD 1973, ZARZYCKI 1976a, 1976b). This method facilitates objective and explicit estimation of indicative value of plants. This method is appropriate when the sample size is small (MÖLLER 1992).

In order to introduce short characteristics of the species, analyzed ecological factors were reduced arbitrarily to digital scale (ELLENBERG 1952, LANDOLT 1977, ELLENBERG et al. 1992, ZARZYCKI et al. 2002) and listed in Table 1. The formula of ecological behavior of *C. brizoides* comprises 14 numbers.

RESULTS

In the area of the Silesian Upland, *Carex brizoides* most frequently occurs in sites with slope from 0 to 20° and variable exposure. The highest frequency of the species was recorded in flat and sloping places (Fig. 2A) with south-western aspect (Fig. 2B). Canopy cover and light conditions occurring in patches with *C. brizoides* vary in wide range from 10 to 90%. Most frequently the plant occurred in thinned tree stands with the coverage of 60–80% (Fig. 2C).

Litter depth in patches with *C. brizoides* ranged from 0 to 8 cm. Most often the studied species occurred in patches where litter depth ranged between 2 and 4 cm (Fig. 2D). Soil humidity varied from 1 to 40%. In most patches with *C. brizoides* soil

Fig. 2. Frequency of *Carex brizoides* due to: A – slope inclination, B – slope aspect, C – tree cover, D – litter depth, E – soil moisture, F – active acidity, G – hydrolytic acidity, H – percentage of floatable parts, I – content of available phosphorus, J – content of available magnesium, K – content of available potassium, L – percentage of total nitrogen, M – percentage of organic carbon, N – conditions for humification of organic matter.

was moist (Fig. 2E). The soil granulometric composition ranges from 5% to more than 50% of floatable parts. The optimum of the occurrence of the species falls in soils of average fertility medium loam (Fig. 2H).

Soil reaction (pH in H₂O) was between 3.2 and 6.8. In most samples it was between 5.6 and 6.0 (Fig. 2F). Exchangeable acidity of soil in patches with the studied sedge was between 3.1 and 6.6, and the most numerous class was between 4.4–5.6 (Fig. 2G).

The content of phosphorus varied between 0.3 and 41.7 mg/100g of soil. In most patches of *C. brizoides*, low and average contents of phosphorus in soils were recorded (Fig. 2I). The content of magnesium ranged from 0.4 to 29.7 mg/100g of soil. *C. brizoides* most frequently occurred on soils with low and average contents of magnesium (Fig. 2J). The content of potassium varied between 0.2 to 21.0 mg/100g of soil. The studied species reached the highest frequency on potassium-deficient soils (Fig. 2K).

The content of total nitrogen ranged from 0.1 to above 0.75%. The highest frequency was recorded in average nitrogen-rich soils (Fig. 2L). The content of organic carbon amounted from 0 to 8%. The most frequent were weakly humus soils (Fig. 2M). The ratio of C : N most frequently was between 10 and 20 (Fig. 2N).

Summarizing information from particular ecodiagrams, local ecological optima for *C. brizoides* were obtained (Table 1). *C. brizoides* is a species that occurs most frequently and with highest abundance in flat areas or on gentle SW facing slopes, under thinned tree stands. The studied sedge prefers acid, moist soils with thin litter and granulometric composition typical for medium loam, with the average content of phosphorus, low and average content of magnesium, low content of potassium. It occurs most frequently on soils with average content of nitrogen, low content of humus, and with average conditions for humification.

DISCUSSION

The obtained results present the conditions of sites with the occurrence of *Carex brizoides* in one geographical region. They were defined on the basis of data collected only in forest communities (SIERKA 2001). This limits the considered ecological amplitude. It also does not permit to draw general conclusions. Nevertheless, the Silesian Upland with respect to its geomorphology and array of habitats seems to be representative area for the estimation of local ecological amplitudes of plants (DIEKMAN 2003), and therefore it facilitates to create a model of their massive spread (ROOZIELIŃSKA 2004).

The obtained values of ecological variables for *C. brizoides* in the Silesian Upland differ from those presented by ELLENBERG et al. (1992) and ZARZYCKI et al. (2002), because scales used by these authors were created due to relative weighting (DZWONKO 2001) of the occurrence conditions of the species in large areas. The differences in values results also from the limitation of studies to disturbed phytocoenoses in the Silesian Upland (CABAŁA 1990, KOMPAŁA-BĄBA and SIERKA 2006). Furthermore, some authors analyzed factors determining the presence of *C. brizoides*, using various scales. Species adapt to changes in environment after some time with certain

Table 1. Ranges of environmental variables recorded for *Carex brizoides* and resulted ecological indicator values (optima) revealed by this species in forest communities of the Silesian Upland.

Variable	Degree						Optima of <i>Carex brizoides</i>
	Z ₁	Z ₂	Z ₃	Z ₄			
Slope inclination (Z) [°] (after: WĘGLARSKI 1991)	0°-1°	2°-5°	6°-10°	11°-20°			Z ₁
Slope aspect (Ex)	N. NE. E. SE. S. SW. W. NW						SW
Tree cover (D) [%] (after: OBMIŃSKI 1977)	D ₁ 0.1-40.0%	D ₂ 40.1-60.0	D ₃ 60.1-80.0	D ₄ >80.0			D ₃
Litter depth (G) [cm]	G ₁ 0-2.0	G ₂ 2.1-4.0	G ₃ 4.1-6.0	G ₄ 6.1-8.0	G ₅ >8.1		G ₂
Moisture (W) [%] (after: UGLLA 1957)	W ₁ 1.0-10.0	W ₂ 10.1-20.0	W ₃ 21.1-30.0	W ₄ >30.0			W ₃
pH _(H₂O) (K _W) (after: LAZAR 1976)	K _{W1} 3.20-4.40	K _{W2} 4.41-5.60	K _{W3} 5.61-6.00	K _{W4} 6.01-6.40	K _{W5} >6.41		K _{W3}
pH _(KCl) (K _C) (after: LAZAR 1976)	K _{C1} 3.10-3.60	K _{C2} 3.61-4.40	K _{C3} 4.41-5.60	K _{C4} 5.61-6.40	K _{C5} 6.41-6.6		K _{C3}
Granulometric composition (S) (content of floatable parts [%]); (after: KUŹNICKI et al. 1979, BORATYŃSKI et al. 1969)	Light soil	Average soil			Heavy soil		S ₅
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	
	5.00-10.00	10.1-15.0	15.1-20.0	20.1-35.0	35.1-50.0	>50.1	
Content of available pho- sphorus (P) [mg/100g of soil]	P ₁ 0.20-7.50	P ₂ 7.51-14.50	P ₃ 14.51-21.0				P ₁
Content of available magne- sium (M) [mg/100g of soil]	M ₁ 0.30-14.00	M ₂ 14.01-28.00	M ₃ 28.01-42.0				M ₂
Content of available po- tassium (K) [mg/100g of soil]	K ₁ 0.40-9.50	K ₂ 9.51-15.50	K ₃ >15.51				K ₁
Content of total nitrogen (N) [%]	N ₁ 0.10-0.25	N ₂ 0.26-0.50	N ₃ 0.51-0.75	N ₄ >0.75			N ₂
Content of organic carbon (C) [%]	C ₁ 0.00-1.00	C ₂ 1.10-2.00	C ₃ 2.01-4.00	C ₄ 4.10-8.00			C ₂
Conditions for humification of matter C/N (after: BOROWIEC 1973)	C/N ₁ 8.00-10.00	C/N ₂ 10.01-20.00	C/N ₃ <20.00				C/N ₂

delay. *C. brizoides* is recorded mainly in human-transformed phytocoenoses and it is considered as an indicator complex of biotopic changes.

High deposition of nitrogen originating from industrial pollution and high deposition of phosphorus are considered as the main factors favoring the occurrence of

C. brizoides in forest communities (SZCZEPANOWICZ 1986, BINKLEY and HÖGGER 1997). It was not confirmed by the optima gained in this study based on frequency of the species in forest phytocoenoses of the Silesian Upland. Both in relation to contents of nitrogen and phosphorus as well as magnesium and particularly potassium *C. brizoides* prefers soils of average richness and nutrient-deficient. It is probably associated with the biological features of this species. The studied sedge uses growth strategy typical for plants of poor habitats developing well in fertile habitats and simultaneously seeks new sites in case of exploitation of nutrients. It seems that *C. brizoides* likewise *Carex arenaria* (NOBLE et al. 1979) stores great amounts of nutrients in its organs. Most of stored nutrients do not return to soil, but are transported from old decaying rhizome to their younger parts and are reused for building new modules. The high rate of exchange of old modules into new ones enables the sedge to occupy new sites. Perhaps *C. brizoides* occurred earlier mainly in poor habitats, but at present it penetrates frequently more fertile biotopes as *Carex arenaria* when soils undergo manuring (NOBLE et al. 1979). The acidity of habitats (pH of soil 4–4.5) is the next factor encouraging the occurrence of the species. It was caused by practices in forest management aiming to cultivation of pine (ANIOŁ-KWIATKOWSKA 1993, CZEREPKO 2004). Along with thinning of tree stands the release of mineral compounds from organic matter is faster and they are more available for *C. brizoides* and favour this species (SIERKA and ORCZEWSKA 2001, ZARZYCKI et al. 2002). The sedge, dominating in herb layer, produces hard-decaying biomass (SZCZEPANOWICZ 1986, PAPLIŃSKA 1987), and hampers the circulation of chemical elements in ecosystem (NOBLE 1979).

The obtained results point at the wide ecological scale of *C. brizoides*, which occupies large spectrum of sites and eliminates species being better indicators of habitat changes. The results of indirect evaluation of habitat conditions on the basis of the occurrence of *C. brizoides* are burdened with big error and this species is not suitable for analyses of habitat conditions using ecological indicators. The phytoindicative importance of the studied sedge, based on its ecological amplitude, is minimal, because it does not meet requirements for phytoindicators i.e. narrow scale of response to specific habitat factor. The research indicate the range of habitats in which this species find favourable conditions for growth and development (SIERKA 2001). Then, the knowledge concerning detailed ecological amplitude of *Carex brizoides* may be used in forest practice for work out the prevention methods or (at least) the limitation of the species massive spread.

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REFERENCES

- ANIOŁ-KWIATKOWSKA J. 1993. Zmiany szaty roślinnej Dolnego Śląska pod wpływem działalności człowieka. Wydawnictwa Uniwersytetu Wrocławskiego, Prace Botaniczne 55: 5–50.

- BINKLEY D., HÖGGER P. 1997. Does atmospheric deposition of nitrogen threaten Swedish forest? *Forest Ecology and Management* 92: 152–199.
- BORATYŃSKI K., CZUBA R., SKOWROŃSKI S. 1969. Wyniki pierwszej rotacji badań odczynu gleb Polski i ich zasobność w przyswajalny fosfor i potas. *Roczniki Gleboznawcze* 22, 2: 347–366.
- BOROWIEC S. 1961. Kryteria glebowe jako podstawa ustalenia siedliskowych typów lasu na obszarze o zniekształconym składzie gatunkowym drzewostanów nadleśnictwa Brynek. *Societas Scientiarum Stetinensis* 5, 2: 1–44.
- BULOKNOW A. D. 1975. *Sarothamnus scoparius* (L.). Wimm. Ex Koch. i *Carex brizoides* Jusl. Ex. L. w Brianskiej oblasti; *Bataničeskij Žurnal*. 60: 872–873.
- CABAŁA S. 1990. Zróżnicowanie i rozmieszczenie zbiorowisk leśnych na Wyżynie Śląskiej. *Prace Naukowe Uniwersytetu Śląskiego, Katowice*, 1068: 1–142.
- CELIŃSKI F., SENDEK A., WIKA S. 1978. Zbiorowiska leśne bogatszych siedlisk Katowickiego Okręgu Przemysłowego. *Prace Naukowe Uniwersytetu Śląskiego, Katowice*, 234: 123–167.
- CELIŃSKI F., CZYŁOK A. 1995. Różnorodność biologiczna i przyrodniczo-krajobrazowa „Uroczyska Głębokie Doły” koło Rybnika. *Scripta Rudensia* 5: 1–52.
- CHMURA D., SIERKA E. 2007. The invasibility of deciduous forest communities after disturbance: A case study of *Carex brizoides* and *Impatiens parviflora* invasion. *Forest Ecology and Management* 242: 487–495.
- CZARNECKA B. 1986. Biological properties of *Majanthemum bifolium* (L.) F.w. Schm. polycormones under various ecological conditions. *Acta Societatis Botanicorum Poloniae*. 55: 659–678.
- CZEREPEKO J. 2004. Development of vegetation in managed Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) stands in an oak–lime–hornbeam forest habitat. *Forest Ecology and Management* 202: 119–130.
- DIEKMAN M. 2003. Species indicator values as an important tool in applied plant ecology – a review. *Basic and Applied Ecology* 4: 1–14.
- DOBRAŃSKI B., UZIĄK S. 1970. Rozpoznawanie i analiza gleb. PWN, Warszawa.
- DOBRAŃSKI B., UZIĄK S., KLIMOWICZ Z., MELKE J. 1987. Badanie gleb w laboratorium i w polu. Przewodnik do ćwiczeń z gleboznawstwa dla studentów biologu i geografii. *Annales UMCS*.
- DZWONKO Z., GAWROŃSKI S. 1994. The role of woodland fragments, soil types, and dominant species in secondary succession on the western Carpathian foothills. *Vegetatio* 111: 149–160.
- DZWONKO Z. 2001. Assessment of light and soil conditions in ancient and recent woodlands by Ellenberg indicator values. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 38: 942–951.
- ELLENBERG H. 1952. *Weisen und Weiden und ihre standortliche Bewertung*. G. Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart-Ludwigsburg.
- ELLENBERG H., WEBER H. E., DULL R., WIRTH V., WERNER W., PAULISEN D. 1992. *Zeigerwerte von Pflanzen in Mitteleuropa*. *Scripta Geobotanica* 18. Verlag Erich Goltze, Göttingen.
- FALIŃSKI J. B. 1998a. Invasive alien plants, vegetation dynamics and neophytism. *Phytocoenosis* 10 (N. S.), *Supplementum Carthographiae Geobotanicae* 9:163–187.
- FALIŃSKI J. B. 1998b. Success of alien species in the process of degeneration and regeneration. In: K. FALIŃSKA (ed.), *Plant population biology and vegetation processes*, p. 204–218. W. Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków.
- GRIME J. P., LLOYD P. S. 1973. *An ecological atlas of grassland plant*. Nature Conservancy (N.E.R.C.), Unit of Grassland Research, London.
- HEREŹNIAK J. 1993. Stosunki geobotaniczno-leśne północnej części Wyżyny Śląsko-Krakowskiej na tle zróżnicowania i przemian środowiska. *Monographiae Botanicae* 75: 1–343.
- IZDEBSKI K. 1972. Zbiorowiska roślinne projektowanego rezerwatu leśnego „Zwierzyńiec”. *Annales UMCS Sec. C* 27: 207–231.
- IZDEBSKI K., KIMS A. T., STRĄCZEK A. 1976. Dynamika zawartości składników mineralnych w runie i glebie wybranych zbiorowisk Roztocza Środkowego. *Annales UMCS, Sec. C* 31,3: 70–78.
- KOŃPAŁA-BĄBA A., SIERKA E. 2006. Przekształcenia środowiska przyrodniczego na skutek działalności przemysłu – spojrzenie biologa. In: E. KANTOWICZ, M. ROGE-WIŚNIEWSKA (eds), *Współczesne tendencje kształcenia w zakresie ochrony środowiska*, p. 81–92. Wyd. Uniwersytet Warszawski, Warszawa.

- KONDRACKI J. 1994. Geografia fizyczna Polski. PWN, Warszawa.
- KROTOSKA T., PIOTROWSKA H. 1962. Dąbrowy na glebach „typu krotoszyńskiego”. *Badania Fizjograficzne nad Polską Zachodnią* 10: 133–183.
- KUŹNICKI F., BIAŁOUSZ S., SKŁADKOWSKI P. 1979. Podstawy gleboznawstwa z elementami kartografii i ochrony gleb. PWN, Warszawa.
- LANDOLT E. 1977. *Ökologische Zeigerwerte zur Schweizer Flora*, Veröffentlichungen Geobotanisches Institut ETH Stiftung Rübel, 125, Zürich.
- LAZAR J. 1976. Gleboznawstwo z podstawami ekologii. PWN, Warszawa–Poznań.
- MÖLLER H. 1992. Zur Verwendung des Medians bei Zeigerwertberechnungen nach Ellenberg. *Tüxenia* 7: 499–505.
- NOBLE J. C., BELL A. D., HARPER J. L. 1979. The population biology of plants with clonal growth. I. The morphology and structural demography of *Carex arenaria*. *Journal of Ecology* 67: 983–1008.
- OLACZEK R. 1974. Kierunki degeneracji fitocenozy leśnych i metody ich badania. *Phytocoenosis* 3, 3/4: 179–190.
- PACZOSKI J. 1900. O formacjach roślinnych i o pochodzeniu flory Poleskiej. *Pamiętnik Fizjograficzny* 16: 3–156.
- PAPLIŃSKA E. 1987. Settlement of *Diptera* larvae in organic matter (*Carex brizoides* L., *Betula verrucosa* Ehrh.) experimentally introduced into the soil. *Polish Ecological Studies* 13, 1: 53–70.
- ROO-ZIELIŃSKA E. 2004. Fitoindykacja jako narzędzie oceny środowiska fizycznogeograficznego. Podstawy teoretyczne i analiza porównawcza stosowanych metod. IGiPZ, PAN im. St. Leszczyńskiego, Warszawa.
- SCAMONI A. 1967. Wstęp do fitosocjologii praktycznej. PWN, Warszawa.
- SIERKA E. 2001. Ekologiczne uwarunkowania występowania *Carex brizoides* na Wyżynie Śląskiej. Ph. D. Thesis, Uniwersytet Śląski, Katowice.
- SIERKA E. 2003. Leśny najeźdźca – turzyca drżączkowata – przyczyny i skutki jej ekspansji w naszych lasach. *Problemy środowiska i jego ochrony, Centrum Studiów nad Człowiekiem i Środowiskiem, Katowice*, 11: 12–24.
- SIERKA E., CHMURA D. 2004. Changes in mixed coniferous forest (*Quercus robur*-*Pinetum*) as a result of forest economy in the Silesian Upland. *Uniwersytet Zielonogórski, Inżynieria Środowiska, Zeszyty Naukowe* 131: 327–334.
- SIERKA E., CHMURA D. 2006. Przemiany zbiorowisk leśnych i ich znaczenie dla ochrony walorów przyrodniczych Rezerwatu Przyrody „Dolina Zabnika” (Wyżyna Śląska). *Chrońmy Przyrodę Ojczyznę* 62, 4: 85–93.
- SIERKA E., ORCZEWSKA A. 2001. Zdegenerowane grądy z *Carex brizoides* L. wybranych obszarów Wyżyny Śląskiej i Płaskowyżu Głubczyckiego. Przemiany środowiska przyrodniczego Polski a jego funkcjonowanie. In: K. GERMAN, J. BALON (eds), *Problemy Ekologii Krajobrazu* 10: 474–480.
- SŁOMKA J. 1958. Przenikanie światła do wnętrza lasu. *Ekologia Polska, Ser. B* 3: 231–236.
- STACHURSKA A. 1998. Zbiorowiska leśne północno-wschodniej części Pogórza Wielickiego, *Zeszyty Naukowe Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego, Prace Botaniczne* 30: 9–78.
- SZCZEPANOWICZ B. 1986. Udział roślin runa w krążeniu pierwiastków mineralnych w grądzie *Tilio-Carpinetum* na Pogórzu Wielickim. Ph. D. Thesis, Uniwersytet Jagielloński, Kraków.
- SZWED W. 1986. Ecological scale of chosen vascular plants of the subalpine and alpine zones in Babia Góra Masif. *Poznańskie Towarzystwo Przyjaciół Nauk, Prace Komisji Biologicznej, Warszawa–Poznań* 69: 1–91.
- VEEN VAN DER K., BREMER P. 1997. Het botanisch onderzoek in Twente. *Nieuwsbrief Flotron-Fwt* 16: 4–9.
- WĘGLARSKI K. 1991. Amplitudy ekologiczne wybranych gatunków roślin naczyniowych Wielkopolskiego Parku Narodowego. *Wyd. Naukowe Uniwersytetu A. Mickiewicza, Poznań*.
- ZARZYCKI K. 1976a. Ecodiagrams of common vascular plants in the Pieniny Mountains (the Polish Western Carpathians). Part I. Ecodiagrams of selected woodland species. *Fragmenta Floristica et Geobotanica* 22, 4: 478–497.
- ZARZYCKI K. 1976b. Ecodiagrams of common vascular plants in the Pieniny Mountains (the Polish Western Carpathians). Part I. Ecodiagrams of selected grassland species. *Fragmenta Floristica et Geobotanica* 22, 4: 501–528.

ZARZYCKI K., TRZCIŃSKA-TACIK H., RÓŻAŃSKI W., SZELĄG Z., WOŁEK J., KORZENIAK U. 2002. Ecological indicator values of vascular plants of Poland. W. Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Science, Kraków.